

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
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- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

Improving the efficiency of investment activity in oil and gas enterprises.....	24
Raxmatova M.G., G'ofurov Sh.N.	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	30
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Xalqaro standartlarning korxonaga eksportini oshishidagi ahamiyati.....	35
Sobitov Diyor Abbralxonovich	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalar boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	40
Ataismatov Iqboljon Zumratjonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida turizm infratuzilmasini innovatsion rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini ekonometrik modellashtirish va prognozlashtirishning ba'zi masalari.....	46
Jumaniyazova Ro'za Quvondiq qizi	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash.....	60
Rasulov Muxammad Bobur Fazliddin o'g'li	
Economic analysis of investment activity of enterprises.....	66
Shermatov Akhror Abduhakimovich	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda innovatsion faoliyatni moliyalashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	72
Z. Rahimova	
Влияние углеродного следа на экологическую устойчивость узбекистана.....	76
Саттарова Барно Шухратовна	
Moliya bozori dastaklari orqali xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish modellarining uslubiy asoslari.....	84
Ibragimov G'anijon G'ayratovich	
Maqsadli tushumlarning audit obyekti sifatidagi tasnifi va tavsifi.....	90
Ne'matov Oybek Ismatullayevich, Qambarov Abduazizbek	
Bank majburiyatlari tushunchasi, uning mazmuni va mohiyati.....	96
Muminova Parvina Ilhom qizi	
Sanoat korxonalariga berilayotgan soliq imtiyozlari ma'murchiligini ta'minlash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar samaradorligi.....	100
Turabov Ulug'bek Olimjonovich	
Tur operatorlari va sayohat agentliklarida xarajatlar va foyda tahlili va uning turlari.....	106
Taniyev Ahmadjon Bahromovich	
O'zbekistonda kredit bozorini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	113
Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich	
Social media marketing as a key strategy in modern business.....	125
Najimova Bakhtigul Abdilkasim qizi	
O'zbekistonda yashil mahsulotlar eksportini rivojlantirish orqali barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish va xalqaro integratsiyani ta'minlash.....	129
Radjabov Bunyod Abduxalilovich	
Оценка и управление рисками в проектах строительства энергетических объектов.....	136
Махматкулов Жамшед Бахтиёрович	
Iqtisodiyotda ko'chmas mulk bozori hamda uning xususiyatlari.....	140
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich, Raimkulov Sherali O'rozdavlatovich, G'ffarov Husayn Aliyor o'g'li, Ismoilov Davronjon Ilxomjon o'g'li, Tashpulatova Shaxnoza Tursunpulatovna	
Ekologik turizmning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ta'siri va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari (Jizzax viloyati misolida).....	144
Isomiddinov Sherzod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Ways to improve personnel policy in improving the quality of financial services provided by financial institutions.....	148
Ergashev Umidjon Ibragimovich	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'ining budjet daromadlarini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati.....	152
Djabbarov Anvar Muxammadsaliyevich	

Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining barqarorlik reytingini aniqlash va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	157
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
Tovar-moddiy zaxiralar auditini tashkil qilish masalalari	164
Turmanqulov Norpo'lat Sa'dullayevich, Botirov Lazizbek Botirovich	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklari faoliyatida aktivlar daromadligini oshirish masalalari.....	168
Saxibjonov Muzaffar Salijanovich	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	174
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Strategic growth of global companies in contemporary environments.....	179
Djurabaev Otabek Djurabayevich	
Directions for management of the tax system.....	184
Sharokhmatov Abdurakhim Abdulamitovich	
Davlat korxonalarida moliyaviy samaradorlik va uni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	188
Qarshiyev Nodirbek Olim o'g'li	
Проблемы, модели и методы оптимизации управления товарными запасами	193
Бабаджанов Шопулат Шомашрабович	
Literature review: the significance of digitization to management credit activity of commercial banks	200
Jo'rayev Eldor Berdibekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining davlat budjeti.....	205
Ajibaeva Raiya Maxsudovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot kontsepsiyasining shakillanishi, taraqqiyot bosqichlari va uning dolzarbligi.....	212
Kodirov Javlonbek Nematullayevich	
Bank plastik kartalari orqali masofaviy xizmatlarni takomillashtirish.....	219
Abdullayeva Dildora Qudratovna, Abdullayev Baxodirjon Valijon o'g'li, Almuratova Nurlio'lmasoy Naim qizi	
O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishni ekonometrik modellashtirish	223
Shamsiyeva Feruza Muratxodjayevna	
Mahalla faoliyati ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil qilishning nazariy asoslari.....	232
Aliqulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda lizing bozori tahlili.....	237
Boyev Bekzodjon Jo'raqul o'g'li, Shavkatov Behruz Rustam o'g'li	
Chakana savdoni rivojlantirishning mintaqaviy xususiyatlari	241
Ismoilov Shohjahon O'tkir o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tibbiy xizmatlarning rivojlanish tendensiyalari, tarkibiy tuzilish tasnifi va marketing segmentlari	244
Axmedov Zafarjon A'zamovich	
Мировой опыт и перспективы развития свободно экономических зон в Республике Узбекистан.....	250
Кадирова Истора Кадирова	
Перспективы реформирования налоговой системы Республики Узбекистан в условиях глобализации.....	254
Буранова Лола Вахобовна, Садиков Искандар Гайратович	
O'zbekiston 2030 strategiyasi – islohotlar tizimligida ipoteka kreditining dolzarbligi.....	263
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari	267
Shoraximova Zilola Nosirdjanovna	
Biologiya va tibbiyotda matematik statistika	271
Voxidov Alikul Melitoshevich	
Kimyo sanoati korxonalarini strategik rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	277
Gulbayeva Feruza Islamovna	
Viloyatda chorvachilik mahsulotlarini o'tgan yilga nisbatan o'zgarishi.....	283
Azimov Allaberdil O'rinovich, Begaliyeva Madina Abdusamatovna	
Servis korxonalarida mobil ilovalar yordamida interaktiv xizmatlar yaratish	289
Ne'matov Nizom Ismatullayevich	

Oziq-ovqat ta'minot zanjiri tushunchasi va uning zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	293
Nazarova A.N	
Влияние искусственного интеллекта при разработке стратегических программ на экономическое развитие страны.....	300
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
Kichik va o'rta biznesda moliyaviy menejment: muammolar va yechimlar.....	306
Saidvaliyeva Nigora Ziyodillayevna	
Теоретико-правовая характеристика экономических отношений.....	313
Фарход Махмудович Тиркашев, Исломжон Жамшедович Жамшедов	
Cash flow reporting in Uzbekistan: national accounting standards and international standards application.....	318
Ochilov Ilyos Keldiyorovich	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyatini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari va takomillashtirish mexanizmlari.....	324
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Получение долгосрочного кредита и определение его размера для привлечения лизинга.....	330
Латипова Шахноза Махмудовна	
Ko'chmas mulk solig'ining ko'chmas mulk bozori tendensiyalariga ta'siri.....	335
To'lakov Ulug'bek Toshmamatovich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarning davlat qarzi va uni boshqarishdagi tajribasini tahlil qilishga ilmiy yondashuv.....	343
Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmuradovich, Abdurahmonova Feruzabonu	
Эффективный инновационный менеджмент в системе здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан.....	353
Абдурахманов З.М.	
Islom moliyasining O'zbekistondagi o'rni va O'zbekiston Respublikasining islomiy tashkilotlar va banklar bilan aloqasi.....	356
Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi, Elboyev Otajon Polvonquliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	361
Oxunjonova Madina Isoqjonovna	
Основные задачи обеспечения цифровой информационной безопасности в образовательном процессе.....	365
Иззатилла Пулатов Кудратиллаевич	
Tijorat banklarida komplaens nazoratni takomillashtirish.....	373
Muminova Marguba Mamirkulovna	
Kichik biznes uchun soliq imtiyozlari va ularning samaradorligi.....	378
Sarvar Ochilov	
Xalqaro moliyaviy tashkilotlarning davlat iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o'rni.....	387
Raxmonova Dildora Ergash qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kreditning iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni.....	395
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Mintaqa sanoat korxonalarida investitsiya jarayonlari rivojlanish tendensiyasining statistik tahlili.....	399
Quvatova Gulzoda Faxriddin qizi	
Natijalarga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish samarali budjet menejmentining omili sifatida.....	403
N. Sheraliev	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznesning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari.....	408
Salayev Jasurbek Komilovich	
Features and prospects for the development of digital marketing in Uzbekistan.....	414
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Анализ динамики импорта узбекистана в 2017–2024 годах с учетом индекса сложности продукции (PCI).....	418
Жабборова Нодира Холмурод кизи	
O'zbekistonning kredit riskini baholash: iqtisodiy barqarorlik va xavf omillari tahlili.....	422
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	

Investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish – korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning muhim shartidir	426
Karimova Dilafuz Sadirdin qizi	
Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faollikni oshirish omillari	431
Qo'ziyev Shodiyor Qilichboy o'g'li, Xakimov Javohir Hamza o'g'li, Turganbaev Nursultan Bayram o'g'li, Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich, Xasanov Ruslan Raxmatovich, Nurullayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность»	437
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
Developing the labor market and strategies for reducing unemployment.....	442
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi, Elmurodov Mukhammadkodir Nurmuhammad	

DEVELOPING THE LABOR MARKET AND STRATEGIES FOR REDUCING UNEMPLOYMENT

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Abstract: This article analyzes labor market development and strategies for reducing unemployment. Current trends in the labor market, causes of unemployment, and influential factors are evaluated through economic-statistical methods. The research proposes recommendations for improving employment rates, creating new job opportunities, and enhancing vocational training.

Key words: Uzbekistan, labor market, unemployment, workforce, employment policies, vocational education, entrepreneurship, digital transformation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mehnat bozorini rivojlantirish va ishsizlikni kamaytirish strategiyalari tahlil etilgan. Mehnat bozoridagi hozirgi tendensiyalar, ishsizlik sabablari va unga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar iqtisodiy-statistik usullar orqali baholangan. Tadqiqot natijasida aholini bandlik bilan ta'minlash, yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish va kasbiy tayyorgarlikni yaxshilash bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekiston, mehnat bozori, ishsizlik, ishchi kuchi, bandlik siyosati, kasb-hunar ta'limi, tadbirkorlik, raqamli transformatsiya.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы развития рынка труда и стратегии сокращения безработицы. Современные тенденции на рынке труда, причины безработицы и влияющие на нее факторы оценены посредством экономико-статистических методов. В результате исследования разработаны рекомендации по обеспечению занятости населения, созданию новых рабочих мест и улучшению профессиональной подготовки.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, рынок труда, безработица, рабочая сила, политика занятости, профессиональное образование, предпринимательство, цифровая трансформация.

INTRODUCTION

The labor market serves as a crucial foundation for economic stability and social welfare, directly influencing the living standards and quality of life of the population. Developing the labor market in Uzbekistan is a priority and a challenge, particularly as the country faces demographic changes, globalization, and technological advancement. Implementing targeted labor policies aimed at reducing unemployment is essential for achieving economic stability and alleviating poverty in Uzbekistan. The relevance of this research is linked to Uzbekistan's economic reforms, which focus on diversifying the economy, enhancing efficiency, and modernizing labor legislation.

Since 2017, Uzbekistan has been undertaking strategic reforms aimed at liberalizing the market, improving the business environment, and attracting foreign investments. These reforms primarily focus on creating jobs in sectors such as agriculture, services, and industry. However, the persistently high unemployment rate, especially among youth and women, indicates the need for deeper strategies to address structural issues within the labor market. Research suggests that Uzbekistan's employment policies must include professional training, skills improvement, and the creation of regional job opportunities to effectively reduce unemployment [11].

One of the main challenges in the Uzbek labor market is the mismatch between skills and available job positions, which is particularly critical for new entrants into the workforce. In recent years, the government has prioritized vocational training programs, implementing educational reforms to align professional training with labor market demands. However, a significant skills gap persists, as many graduates lack the practical competencies required by employers. In response, the government is collaborating with international organizations to support initiatives aimed at improving vocational education and providing job opportunities for youth. Furthermore, expanding the information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure is vital for

developing the labor market, as digital skills are increasingly necessary to meet the rapidly changing demands of the global economy [12].

This research analyzes the development of Uzbekistan's labor market and explores effective strategies for reducing unemployment. Drawing on international best practices and existing studies, this analysis provides a deeper understanding of the challenges in Uzbekistan's labor market and presents recommendations aimed at enhancing employment. The research supports Uzbekistan's broad goals of economic growth, social inclusivity, and poverty reduction, ultimately contributing to a more stable and prosperous future for the country.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The labor market landscape in Central Asia and Eastern Europe is shaped by a complex interplay of socio-economic challenges, regulatory frameworks and evolving technological demands. The studies reviewed in this section offer valuable insights into the labor market dynamics of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Poland and Russia highlighting the pressing issues of employment stability, skill mismatches and regional disparities.

T. Mamatkulov's (2021) study examines labor market reforms and challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic [6]. Utilizing data from 2020, the research analyzes measures taken to maintain employment, considering demographic factors and providing support for the unemployed. It critically assesses government initiatives such as the 2020 Law on Employment, which aims to enhance employability and promote self-employment through digital platforms. Mamatkulov highlights the positive impact of these measures on employment stability and emphasizes the necessity of an information system to connect job seekers with available opportunities. Recommendations include creating new job opportunities and developing digital infrastructure to facilitate this process.

G. Bazarova's (2023) research explores labor market dynamics and issues in the context of the growing digital economy [1]. This study analyzes labor demand and supply, urban-rural employment disparities, and trends in entrepreneurship. Bazarova identifies significant factors affecting labor market development and proposes recommendations to enhance the market's adaptability and resilience, including increasing investments in digital infrastructure and policies that support rural employment. Her findings stress the importance of adapting to digital trends for sustainable labor market development.

U. Narmanov's (2020) research focuses on the role of small businesses in preserving employment [7]. Drawing on data from early 2020, it discusses the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, noting that small businesses account for nearly 60% of GDP. Narmanov evaluates government measures such as tax incentives aimed at fostering small enterprises and emphasizes the importance of leveraging local resources for business adaptability. He concludes with recommendations for broader governmental support and training for entrepreneurs, aiming to create a more favorable business environment that can effectively respond to economic challenges.

S. Khalmuratov's (2022) research examines the regional characteristics of labor resources and labor markets in Uzbekistan [5]. Utilizing recent data, the study evaluates the demographic and economic factors influencing labor distribution and employment levels across various regions, drawing insights from the State Statistics Committee and the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations. Khalmuratov's analysis reveals disparities in employment levels, particularly highlighting the significant challenges faced in rural areas due to limited industrial development and a high reliance on agriculture. Key factors affecting labor resources include demographic changes, urban migration, and specific labor demands. The findings indicate that regions such as Fergana exhibit higher labor participation rates due to industrial diversity, while areas like Sirdarya demonstrate lower participation due to constrained industrial activity. The study offers strategic recommendations for optimizing labor resource utilization, advocating for modernization in agriculture, enhanced industrial support, and the development of local industries. Additionally, it suggests the improvement of vocational education programs tailored to regional labor market needs to balance employment opportunities and reduce disparities.

Sh. Ergasheva, G. Razikova, M. Umarova, A. Nabixodjayev, and U. Salikhodjaeva (2025) provide an in-depth analysis of the labor market infrastructure in Uzbekistan, identifying social and economic challenges that hinder its effectiveness [4]. The researchers evaluate the interplay between labor demand and supply, migration, and the efficiency of employment services. The study indicates that Uzbekistan's labor market must enhance its infrastructure and implement targeted policies to meet modern economic demands, particularly through digital transformation. Key conclusions emphasize that state initiatives should focus on creating a competitive labor environment, improving access to employment opportunities, and tailoring workforce training to industry needs. The study also recommends modernizing employment services and integrating digital tools to enhance data collection and streamline employment processes. Furthermore, it advocates for strengthening vocational training programs and active employment policies to reduce unemployment and increase labor

force participation. These strategies are deemed pivotal for supporting sustainable employment and adapting Uzbekistan's labor market to future economic requirements.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the research is to comprehensively study the development of Uzbekistan's labor market and strategies for reducing unemployment. The key areas of the study include assessing the current state of the labor market, identifying existing challenges, and developing effective countermeasures.

The research utilized both primary and secondary data through dynamic and empirical analysis methods. In the dynamic analysis, significant indicators of Uzbekistan's labor market were examined to uncover trends in employment levels and the dynamics of labor resources in recent years. This analysis, based on official statistical data, helped identify key problems in the labor market and outline necessary directions for ensuring future economic stability.

Additionally, an empirical analysis was conducted using a survey designed to collect data and analyze results. This methodological choice allowed for the examination of the real opinions and experiences of various groups engaged in the labor market, including unemployed citizens, young specialists, entrepreneurs, and industry experts. Respondents from diverse regions of Uzbekistan were included, enhancing the reliability and scope of the findings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Labor resources refer to the total size of the population that can be employed in the economy. From 2010 to 2023, labor resources in Uzbekistan have consistently increased (Figure 1). In 2010, this figure was 16.7 million people, and by 2023, it had risen to 19.7 million people [14]. This growth is associated with natural population increase, migration trends, and an increase in the share of the youth population that is capable of working. The increase in labor resources necessitates strengthening employment policies and creating new job opportunities (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Number of Labor resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2010-2023, thousand people).

The employment rate reflects the proportion of the population that is employed in the country. Between 2010 and 2023, the employment rate experienced various changes (see Figure 2). In 2010, the employment indicator in the republic was 66.9%, which increased to 69.2% by 2017. However, during the pandemic in 2020, this figure dropped to 66%. By 2023, it had returned to a level of 67.9%. The initial decline in the employment rate occurred in 2018, showing a significant decrease compared to 2017. The recovery seen in 2018 was followed by a sharp decline to 66% due to the economic difficulties caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, which resulted in reduced production and a decrease in job opportunities. Starting from 2021, an economic recovery process has been observed (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Employment rate in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2010-2023, %).

The unemployment rate indicates the proportion of the labor force that is unable to find work. Between 2010 and 2016, the unemployment rate was around 5% (see Figure 3). By 2018, it increased to 9.3%, and in 2020, due to the pandemic's impact, it reached its highest level of 10.5%. Starting from 2021, the unemployment rate began to decline as a result of economic recovery, dropping to 6.8% in 2023. The decrease in unemployment is linked to the expansion of employment programs and the creation of new job opportunities (fig. 3).

Figure 3. Unemployment Rate in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2010-2023, %).

Taking into account labor market trends, several important measures are being implemented to increase employment and reduce the unemployment rate. The development of production sectors, support for entrepreneurship, and the strengthening of vocational education are aimed at creating jobs and increasing workforce participation. Additionally, the growth in labor resources necessitates further improvement of employment policies.

These statistical data serve as a basis for a deeper analysis of labor market stability, workforce mobility, and economic recovery processes. Understanding how employment and unemployment rates have changed over the years plays a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency of the labor market.

The survey conducted to deeply analyze the current state of the labor market in Uzbekistan and strategies for reducing unemployment encompasses extensive information. This section provides a detailed analysis of respondents' opinions, the main problems in the labor market, and the proposed solutions.

A total of 222 respondents participated in the survey. The gender distribution of respondents revealed that 158 (71.2%) were men, while 64 (28.8%) were women (see Table 1). These results indicate a relatively higher participation of men in the labor market, which does not necessarily reflect a lack of job opportunities for women. This gender ratio may be influenced by family commitments, traditional views, and gender issues in the labor market (table 1).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics.

Category	Sub-Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	158	71.2%
	Female	64	28.8%
Age group	18-25 years	168	75.7%
	26-35 years	42	18.9%
	36-45 years	10	4.5%
	46 years and older	2	0.9%
Employment status	Employed in permanent work	103	46.4%
	Unemployed	70	31.5%
	Workers in the informal sector	49	22.1%
Occupational status	Teacher	18	8.1
	Employee	18	8.1
	Entrepreneur	28	12.6
	Student	73	32,9
	Doctor	14	6.3
	Housewife and self-employed workers	71	32

The age composition of the respondents is also worthy of attention. Among the participants in the survey, 75.7% (168 individuals) were aged 18-25 (see Table 1). This highlights the need to pay special attention to the difficulties faced by young people entering the labor market. Respondents in the 26-35 age range comprised 18.9% (42 individuals), and those in this age group typically have work experience but may encounter problems related to stable employment. Respondents aged 36-45 made up 4.5% (10 individuals), while those aged 46 and older accounted for 0.9% (2 individuals). This statistical data indicates that the survey primarily included young specialists, which allows for a better understanding of the situation of young people in the labor market.

According to the research results, the employment status of the respondents varies. Among them, 46.4% (103 individuals) are employed in permanent jobs, 31.5% (70 individuals) are unemployed, and 22.1% (49 individuals) are engaged in the informal sector (see Table 1). Most of the respondents who are employed expressed dissatisfaction with their jobs or mentioned low wages. The high number of workers in the informal sector indicates their lack of social protection, meaning they do not have access to pensions, medical insurance, or other social benefits. The high unemployment rate further suggests that formal employment systems are not sufficiently effective for young people.

The occupational status of the respondents is also significant. The study showed that 32.9% (73 individuals) of the participants are students, while 32% (71 individuals) are homemakers and self-employed workers. Entrepreneurs accounted for 12.6% (28 individuals), employees in government organizations comprised 8.1% (18 individuals), while doctors and teachers also constituted 6.3% (14 individuals) and 8.1% (18 individuals), respectively. These figures illustrate the diversification of the labor market and confirm that there are various professional categories among job seekers.

The complexity of the job search process and the numerous obstacles associated with it are also clearly evident from the survey results. The main problems faced by job seekers are distributed as follows (see Figure 3):

- Low Wages: 26.6% (59 individuals) of respondents identified insufficient wages as the biggest problem in finding a job. This suggests that there is a need to reassess the wage system in labor market reforms.
- Lack of Job Openings: 19.4% (43 individuals) of respondents consider the scarcity of job openings to be a primary issue in their job search.
- Skills Gap: 14.9% (33 individuals) highlighted the difference between their professional qualifications and market demands as a significant problem.
- The Need for Connections: 14.4% (32 individuals) noted a lack of trust in formal employment systems, indicating that finding a job through connections has become a common practice.
- Inadequate Working Conditions: 11.7% (26 individuals) reported that poor working conditions or non-compliance with safety standards were significant problems.
- Inconvenient Working Hours: 9.9% (22 individuals) identified issues related to work schedules or flexibility as a challenge in their job search (fig. 4).

Figure 4. Main problems in the job search process.

According to the survey results, the majority of respondents prefer to act independently in their job searches. Specifically, 39.2% (87 individuals) reported being employed through opening their own business or self-employment (Figure 4). Meanwhile, 26.6% (59 individuals) indicated that they found jobs through connections, while 14.9% (33 individuals) searched for jobs using online platforms (such as hh.uz, SuperJob, LinkedIn). Additionally, 13.1% (29 individuals) contacted State Employment Centers, and 6.2% (14 individuals) utilized the services of recruitment agencies. However, only a very small portion – 0.2% (1 individual) – found employment through family connections.

These results indicate that a significant number of job seekers rely on informal channels, with connections and independent entrepreneurship remaining the primary pathways. At the same time, it is evident that seeking jobs online and contacting State Employment Centers are also relevant methods (fig. 5).

Figure 5. Main job-seeking methods.

In the survey, respondents made the following suggestions for reducing the unemployment rate:

Developing and supporting entrepreneurship – 43.7% (97 individuals)

Creating new jobs by the government – 44.1% (98 individuals)

Developing skills enhancement courses – 26.1% (58 individuals)

Attracting investments and developing industry – 35.1% (78 individuals)

Expanding regional employment programs – 22.5% (50 individuals)

Developing large industrial projects – 23.4% (52 individuals)

The majority of respondents expressed the need to strengthen actions in these areas moving forward.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The research results indicate that while the labor market in Uzbekistan has achieved significant development in recent years, problems still persist. A series of reforms aimed at job creation, entrepreneurship development, and improvements in vocational education have been implemented in recent years. Specifically, programs such as the “Youth Employment Support Program”, the “Entrepreneurship Support Fund” and “Job Placement Monocenters” have been launched, positively impacting the labor market. Measures taken by the government to create new jobs and encourage entrepreneurs have also opened up many opportunities for job seekers.

At the same time, the research results clearly highlight the existing problems in the labor market. Difficulties in the employment process, low wages, the influence of connections, and a lack of qualifications were noted by respondents as the most significant issues. Many job seekers reported facing difficulties finding work through formal employment systems, while some emphasized that they had to work in the informal sector. The system for training specialists who meet labor market demands has not yet been fully established, directly impacting youth employment.

The survey results showed that most respondents emphasized their reliance on informal methods rather than formal systems to find jobs. Specifically, finding jobs through connections, self-employment, and engaging in independent entrepreneurship were identified as the most common occurrences. This indicates a need to further develop the formal employment system in the labor market, simplify and improve job search mechanisms, and make them more transparent.

Furthermore, the research revealed a lack of vocational skills among youth that align with labor market demands. The gap between employers' requirements and the actual qualifications of young specialists hinders their access to the employment system. This highlights the need to adjust higher education and vocational training to meet the real needs of the labor market.

Therefore, to further develop the labor market in Uzbekistan, reduce unemployment, and expand employment opportunities, the following recommendations were proposed:

Enhance existing programs in the labor market – Although numerous reforms have been undertaken to improve employment in recent years, increasing their effectiveness is essential. Specifically, it is necessary to expand the operations of “Job Placement Monocenters” aimed at youth employment and simplify the system for providing loans and grants to support entrepreneurship.

Further support entrepreneurship – It is crucial to improve the working conditions of self-employed citizens, provide them with tax benefits, and simplify the processes of starting a business to create new jobs. Particularly, mechanisms for providing start-up capital and grants to youth for entrepreneurship need enhancement.

Make the hiring process transparent and reduce informal employment – The processes of job searching should be facilitated by developing state employment centers and online platforms. Strengthening labor legislation is necessary to prevent corruption and reduce instances of finding jobs through connections.

Reform the vocational education system – Collaboration between employers and educational institutions must be strengthened, and higher education systems need to be aligned with labor market requirements. Offering short-term courses in high-demand areas at vocational training centers should expand youth job placement opportunities.

Expand regional employment programs – Considering the high levels of unemployment, especially in rural areas, specific programs for developing industry and services in villages should be devised. Additionally, it is necessary to modernize employment centers at the regional level and create a more accessible system for job seekers.

Improve working conditions and increase wages – Enhancing working conditions for employees, improving labor legislation, and increasing the minimum wage are essential to boost public interest in the formal employment system. Furthermore, incentives for employers should be introduced to motivate them to join the formal employment system.

The implementation of these proposals will significantly reduce the unemployment level in Uzbekistan's labor market and make the employment system more effective. By ensuring labor market stability, narrowing

the gap between job seekers and employers, and strengthening the vocational training system, economic growth rates can be further improved.

In the future, the labor market in Uzbekistan should be developed with more innovative approaches and digital technologies. By creating transparent and accessible conditions for job seekers, supporting entrepreneurship, and increasing wages, it is possible to enhance the economic well-being of society. The results of this research serve as an important scientific foundation for defining future reforms in the labor market and implementing best practices.

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